

Oxytryptamines¹

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The base-catalyzed condensation of oxindoles with ethyl N,N-dialkylglycinates and the palladium-catalyzed hydrogenation of the resultant 3-acyloxindoles under the influence of acid leads to oxytryptamines, whose reduction with lithium aluminium hydride yields tryptamines. The alkaloids N,N-dimethyltryptamine and O-methylbufotenine have been prepared in this manner.

THE alkaloids N,N-dimethyltryptamine (4a) and O-methylbufotenine (4b) from the Brazilian plants *Mimosa hostilis* Benth. (and various *Piptadenia* species²) and *Dictyoloma incanescens* D. C.³, respectively, have been synthesized by way of oxindole intermediates and by a scheme potentially useful as a general route of tryptamine synthesis.

An alternate, longer path from 3-acyloxindole 2a to oxytryptamine 3a⁸ involved hydrogenation in the absence of acid, acid-induced dehydration of the resultant alcohol 5a and hydrogenation of the 3-alkylideneoxindole 6a. This reaction sequence as well as the above one-step reduction were applicable also to the conversion of 7 into 8. Whereas the single-step

The starting materials were oxindole (1b) and 5-methoxyoxindole (1d)⁴, prepared by the acid-catalyzed isomerization of N-hydroxyoxindole (1b)^{5,6} and diazomethane treatment of the resultant 5-hydroxyoxindole (1c)⁷. Their condensation^{8,9} with ethyl N,N-dimethylglycinate yielded 3-acyloxindoles (2) whose hydrogenation-hydrogenolysis under the influence of palladium and acid led to oxytryptamines (3). Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the latter¹⁰ produced the alkaloids (4).

hydrogenation-hydrogenolysis has been reported to take place without acid catalysis⁹, the product of this reaction was shown to be the alcohol 5b.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ultraviolet spectra on 95% ethanol solutions were recorded on a Cary 14 spectrophotometer and infrared spectra on Nujol pastes were taken on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer.

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5-Hydroxyoxindole (1c): A solution of N-hydroxyoxindole (1b)⁶ (2.00 g) and concentrated sulfuric acid (6 ml) in water (25 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen for 1 hr. The hot solution was treated with charcoal and filtered. Upon cooling the filtrate yielded 1.00 g of precipitate whose sublimation led to 5-hydroxyoxindole (1c), m. p. 265° dec. (lit.⁷ m. p. 270° dec.).

5-Methoxyoxindole (1d): A solution of 5-hydroxyoxindole (1c) (500 mg) in methanol (5 ml) and an excess of diazomethane in ether (50 ml) was kept at 0° for 9 days. Evaporation of the solvents and crystallization of the solid residue from cyclohexane-acetone yielded 5-methoxyoxindole (1d) (490 mg), m. p. 149-51° (lit.⁴ m. p. 152-154°).

3-(α -Hydroxy- β -(N, N-dimethylamino)-ethylidene)-oxindole (2a): A mixture of oxindole (1a) (2.40 g), ethyl N, N-dimethylglycinate (3.00 g) and sodium ethoxide (from 0.60 g of sodium) in 25 ml of absolute ethanol was refluxed for 3.5 hr. A water solution of the precipitated sodium salt was neutralized with solid carbon dioxide and the resultant precipitate (3.40 g) filtered. Crystallization of the latter from benzene-methanol yielded oxindole 2a, m. p. 250-255° dec., IR NH 3.10 (w), C=O, C=C, 6.18 (m), 6.50 (s) μ ; UV λ_{max} 264 nm (log ϵ 4.25), 310 (4.25). *Anal.* found: C, 65.90; H, 6.56; N, 12.74% (calc. for C₁₂H₁₄O₂N₂: C, 66.03; H, 6.47; N, 12.84%).

3-(α -Hydroxy- β -(N, N-dimethylamino)-ethylidene)-5-methoxyoxindole (2b): The same procedure applied to 5-methoxyoxindole (1d) led to a 70% yield of oxindole 2b, m. p. 225-228° (crystallization from benzene-methanol); IR NH 2.95 (w), C=O, C=C 6.10 (m), 6.19 (m), 6.28 (m), 6.50 (s) μ ; UV λ_{max} 282 nm (log ϵ 4.19), 320 (4.00). *Anal.* found: N, 11.58% (calc. for C₁₃H₁₄O₃N₂: N, 11.28%).

3-(β -(N, N-Dimethylamino)-ethyl)-oxindole (3a): A mixture of 2a (800 mg) and palladium-charcoal (80 mg, 30%) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) containing a stoichiometric quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid was hydrogenated at room temperature and atmospheric pressure for 24 hr. It then was filtered and the filtrate evaporated under vacuum. The residual, viscous oil solidified on standing and was crystallized from ether-methanol. The hydrochloride was converted into a perchlorate by neutralization with ammonia, dissolution of the free base in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) and dropwise addition of 70% perchloric acid to the solution. Crystallization of the salt (750 mg, 71%) from benzene-methanol yielded 3a perchlorate, m. p. 130-132°; IR NH 3.03 (m), C=O 5.97 (s), C=C 6.19 (m) μ ; UV λ_{max} 250 nm (log ϵ 3.86), 280 (3.10). *Anal.* found: C, 47.58; H, 5.72; N, 9.04% (calc. for C₁₂H₁₇O₈N₂Cl: C, 47.29; H, 5.62; N, 9.13%).

Hydrogenation of an ethanol solution of 6a perchlorate over palladium-charcoal (30%) at room temperature

and atmospheric pressure gave a quantitative yield of 3a perchlorate, m. p. 130-132°; spectra identical with those of the above sample.

3-(β -(N, N-Dimethylamino)-ethyl)-5-methoxyoxindole (3b): The 2a-3a conversion was applied to 2b and led to a 75% yield of a colourless solid whose crystallization from methanol gave 3b perchlorate, m. p. 180-181°; IR NH 2.99 (m), C=O 5.97 (s), C=C 6.20 (m) μ ; UV λ_{max} 248 nm (log ϵ 4.01), 302 (3.28). *Anal.* found: C, 46.53; H, 5.83; N, 8.19% (calc. for C₁₃H₁₉O₈N₂Cl: C, 46.66; H, 5.73; N, 8.37%).

Conversion of oxindoles 3 into indoles 4: An anhydrous methanolic solution of the oxindole amine salt was made alkaline with methanolic potassium hydroxide and evaporated at room temperature under vacuum. An excess of lithium aluminium hydride was added to a tetrahydrofuran solution of the residue and the mixture refluxed for 0.5 hr. After the customary work-up the crude product was subjected to a second, like hydride treatment. The amine product was converted into its picrate.

N, N-Dimethyltryptamine (4a): Use of this procedure on oxindole 3a gave in 50% yield indole 4a picrate, m. p. 168-170° (lit.¹¹ m. p. 170-171°). Passage of a methanolic solution of the latter through a basic ion exchange resin and crystallization of the liberated organic base from hexane yielded crystalline, colourless 4a, m. p. 45-47° (lit.¹¹ m. p. 49-50°); UV λ_{max} 222 nm (log ϵ 4.58), 275 (3.77), 282 (3.80), 292 (3.74).

O-Methybufotenine (4b): When the procedure was applied to oxindole 3b, there was obtained a 58% yield of 4b picrate, m. p. 175-177° (lit.³ m. p. 176-177.5°). Conversion of the latter into its free amine and crystallization thereof from hexane gave 4b, m. p., m. m. p. 66-68° (lit.³ m. p. 67.5-68.5°); IR and UV spectra identical with those of an authentic sample^{1,2}.

3-(α -Hydroxy- β -(N, N-dimethylamino)-ethyl)-oxindole (5a): A mixture of amine 2a perchlorate (200 mg, m. p. 177-182°) and palladium-charcoal (30 mg, 30%) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was hydrogenated at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. After the uptake of one mole of hydrogen the mixture was filtered and the filtrate evaporated under vacuum below 40°, yielding a heat-sensitive, colourless solid (200 mg of 5a perchlorate whose crystallization from alcohol turned the substance yellow, presumably with the formation of 6a) possessing a melting range of 173-185°; IR OH 2.90 (w), NH 3.06 (w), C=O 6.00 (s), C=C 6.17 (m) μ ; UV λ_{max} 252 nm (log ϵ 4.01), 282 (3.45). *Anal.* found: N, 8.63% (calc. for C₁₂H₁₇O₈N₂Cl: N, 8.74%).

3-(α -Hydroxy- β -(N-piperidino)-ethyl)-oxindole (5b): Hydrogenation of 7 perchlorate by the same procedure and crystallization of the product from benzene-methanol gave a quantitative yield of colourless,

heat-sensitive 5b perchlorate, melting range 165-185°; IR OH 2.89 (w), NH, 3.04 (w), C=O 5.99 (s) C=C 6.15 (w) μ ; UV λ_{max} 250 nm (log ϵ 4.18), 280 (3.41), *Anal.* found: C, 50.07; H, 6.00; N, 7.64% (calc. for C₁₅H₂₁O₆N₂Cl: C, 49.93; H, 5.87; N, 7.77%).

3-(β -(*N,N*-Dimethylamino-) ethylidene-) oxindole (6a): A mixture of 5a perchlorate (200 mg) and perchloric acid (one drop of 70%) in acetic acid (5 ml) was heated at 100° until solution was effected. Cooling of the solution led to a yellow precipitate (128 mg, m.p. 147-154°) whose crystallization from absolute ethanol yielded yellow, crystalline 6a perchlorate, m.p. 152-155°; IR NH 3.06 (m), C=O, C=C 5.91 (s), 6.07 (m), 6.17 (m), μ ; UV λ_{max} 253 nm (log ϵ 4.43), 292 (3.72). *Anal.* found: C, 47.69; H, 5.20; N, 9.23% (calc. for C₁₂H₁₅O₅N₂Cl: C, 47.61; H, 5.00; N, 9.25%).

3-(β -(*N*-Piperidino-) ethylidene-) oxindole (6b): Application of this procedure to 5b perchlorate and crystallization of the product (65%) from methanol yielded yellow, crystalline 6b perchlorate. m.p. 200-204°; IR NH 3.12 (m), C=O, C=C 5.89 (s), 6.00 (m), 6.18 (m) μ ; UV λ_{max} 250 nm (log ϵ 4.39), 258 (4.38), 288 (3.79). *Anal.* found: C, 52.23; H, 5.60; N, 8.50% (calc. for C₁₅H₁₉O₅N₂Cl: C, 52.56; H, 5.59; N, 8.17%).

When a solution of crude 5b perchlorate, prepared above from 7 perchlorate, was evaporated at 100°, yellow 6b perchlorate was produced. The latter, m.p., m.m p. 200-204°, was identical spectrally with the compound assumed heretofore to have been 8 perchlorate⁹.

3-(β -(*N*-Piperidino-) ethyl-) oxindole (8): Hydrogenation of 6b perchlorate according to the above procedure of the 6a-3a conversion and transformation of the product into a picrate gave a quantitative yield

of 8 picrate, m.p. 195-198°. *Anal.* found: C, 53.32; H, 5.01; N, 15.77% (calc. for C₂₁H₂₄O₈N₆: C, 53.27; H, 4.89; N, 15.79%).

Hydrogenation of 7 under conditions of the above 2a-3a conversion produced 8 picrate (75% yield), m.p. 195-198°. Liberation of the free base and treatment of an anhydrous ether solution of the latter with hydrogen chloride gas yielded a precipitate, whose crystallization from a dry methanol-ether mixture led to 8 hydrochloride, m.p. 193-196°; IR NH 3.15 (m), NH⁺ 3.78(m), 3.92 (m), C=O 5.85(s), C=C 6.20(m) μ ; UV λ_{max} 249 nm (log ϵ 3.92).

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